

The Effect of Religious Tourist Motivation and Satisfaction on Behavioral Intention

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Abstract—In recent years, the Chaoshan area, a special place located in the southeast of Guangdong province in China, actively protects religious heritage and is developing religious tourism, which is attracting many expatriate Chinese who are coming back for travel and to worship. This paper discussed three questions. Firstly, what is the current situation about the different social background of tourists' motivation, satisfaction and behavioral intention? Secondly, is there a relationship between the motivation, satisfaction and behavioral intention and the different social backgrounds of tourists? Thirdly, what is the relationship between religious tourists' motivation, satisfaction and behavioral intention? The research methods use a combination of qualitative analysis and quantitative analysis. Qualitative analysis uses the method of observation and interviews. Convenient sampling technique was used for quantitative analysis. The study showed that the different social backgrounds of tourists' forms diverse cognition and experiences about religious tourism, and their motivations, satisfaction and behavioral intention as tourists vary. Tourists' motivation and satisfaction has a positive phase relation. Tourists' motivation with satisfaction as the intervening variable also has a positive phase effect on tourists' behavior intention. The result shows that religious tourists' motivations include experiencing a religious atmosphere, and having a rest and recreation. The result also shows that religious tourists want to travel with their family members and friends. While traveling, religious tourists like to talk with Buddhist monks or nuns. Compared to other tourism types, religious tourists have higher expectations about temple environment, traveling experience, peripheral service and temple management.

Keywords—Behavioral intension, motivation, religious tourism, satisfaction.

I. INTRODUCTION

CHAOSHAN, also known as Chiusaan in Cantonese, is a region with a unique geographical location in Guangdong province in China. Its special location gives the region a unique religious culture. Therefore, in recent years, the government has been working actively to protect its religious heritage and try to develop local religious tourism, which has encouraged the return of many expatriate Chinese wanting to visit to fulfill both nostalgic and religious desires and obligations. However, multiple religious cultures make it difficult to determine how to develop local religious tourism successfully. This study tried to examine the relationship between religious tourists' motivation, satisfaction and behavioral intention. Firstly, to understand the status related to different social economic backgrounds of visitors' motivation, satisfaction and behavioral intentions; Secondly, to understand whether

correlations exist between the different social economic backgrounds of visitor's motivation, satisfaction and behavioral intentions; Thirdly, to understand the different social economic backgrounds of the relationship between motivation, satisfaction and behavioral intention.

The paper will address four purposes of the research: First, it will understand the motivation of the different social economic visitors who go to Chaoshan temple. Second, it will understand the satisfaction of the different social economic visitors who go to Chaoshan temple. Third, it will understand the behavioral intention of the different social economic visitors who go to Chaoshan temple. Fourth, it will understand the relationship between motivation, satisfaction and behavioral intention. This research aims to improve the quality and development of Chaoshan religious tourism.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Religious Tourism

Religious reasons are strong and exclusive motivators for religious tourism [1]. The religion of our country combined with ecological culture, natural scene and historical sites. So, in the early days, the religion and tourism of our country have already formed mutually promoting and developing together. The definition of religious tourism in this research is made up of two parts. The first one is that the believers participate in activities of religion because of religion's purpose. The second one is that the non-believers go to the scenic spot experiencing religion's culture and having a rest. In the narrow sense, the first segment of tourists includes the believers participating in activities of religion because of religion's purpose, such as pilgrimage, request teaching, teaching and wandering. Religion, heritage and travel are linked each other [2]. One is that the believers go to the holy land of religion in Chaoshan to chant, pilgrimage, and cultivate morality. And another one is that the non-believers visit temples and experience cultural sensibilities and spiritual fulfillment in tourism. Sun Jianhong, has published a relevant article, in which he pointed out that for the special geographical position, because of many uncertainties, such as the weather or sea, people entrust their fortune to gods. The diversification of identity in Chaoshan religion encourages people promote this special culture in social construction and life. It is Chaoshan people's precious spiritual resource. Taoism, Buddhism worship and folk-belief are three major parts of Chaoshan religious belief. Chaoshan religion cultural renaissance and the support of overseas Chinese are inseparable. In recent years, Chaoshan's famous monks travel the world to promote cultural communication and make friends. This promotion is carried out for several religious

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tourism areas, like Chaoshan, which benefit from the religious development and tourism development of Chaoshan.

B. Tourist Motivation

Motivation is a kind of behavior after the tourists have the idea of demand. The generation of the tourists' needs come from the individual's curiosity for exploring scenic spots. Another reason could be to escape the everyday pressures of life, from work or home, tourists travel to relax. Dann divided the motivation into two concepts [3], these are: Thrust motivation, which will influence whether visitors will travel or not. And pull motivation is what decides the tourist destination. The motivations are the tourists' plans and urge from the outset, which decides the destination they will go to. This research grounded in the scholars' research results and an analysis of religion in Chaoshan. The motivation for religious tourism in Chaoshan is evidenced by the fact that people leave their home environment to visit the tourist sites. Influenced by outside world, tourists are attracted to participate in some religion's activities, and harvest faith and meet their need for relaxation and recreation.

C. Tourist Satisfaction

The unique character of tourists produces different triggers for satisfaction of travel experiences [4]. Satisfaction is a psychological emotional assessment made by the visitors. Visitors' needs, interests, attitudes and motivation will influence the way of traveling and form the different travel experiences; thus, every tourist has different satisfaction. Environmental characteristics, personal recreation, and the quality of participate in activities are the subjective assessment of entire traveling process which can influence the level of satisfaction [5]. Satisfaction is a sudden and short psychic reaction in particular cases which emerges in the service that people got and the perceived value of the travel. This paper researches the level of tourists' satisfaction after having a religious tourist satisfaction in Chaoshan. The study does not compare early expectation and travel experience.

D. Behavioral Intention

Tourists make subjective judgments about the behavior that will happen in the future after visiting tourism destinations [5]. One type of the subjective judgments is about revisit intention, loyalty and recommendation intention, the second type includes complaints and negative word of mouth and departure, etc. This paper aims to define the behavior intention of tourists in making a judgment about whether the travel experience was good enough after the trip. It can help us to understand whether the tourists will revisit and recommend, or if they will complain and not go again.

III. METHOD

This study used quantitative analysis and qualitative methods to check the relationship among religious tourists' motivation, satisfaction and behavioral intention. The quantitative analysis method of the investigation is based on the convenience of selecting a sample survey manner. The

questionnaires were given to the tourists who come to the temple in Chaoshan area. Items in the questionnaire include social economic information to understand visitors. A Likert scale was used to collect data on the religious tourist's motivation, satisfaction, and behavioral intention. After the questionnaires were collected, we performed descriptive statistics, reliability analysis, validity analysis, factor analysis, single factor analysis of variance, analysis of variance, regression analysis, and correlation analysis to check the relationships of different variables.

The author used the data gathered about religious tourists who visited Chaoshan temple to observe and study the period from 2015 to 2016. And the author chose nine visitors and staff as interview subjects. There are many temples in Chaoshan district such as Shantou, Chaozhou and Jieyang. These three cities are usually associated with the Chaoshan region because of their common dialect and cultural traditions. The aim of the study is to understand the tourists' age, gender, marital status, occupation, education level, tourist's origin place, religious beliefs, visiting frequency, visiting companion, and holiday duration.

TABLE I
 PROFILE OF THE RESPONDENTS

respondents	items	number	percentage (%)
Gender	male	157	40.5
	female	231	59.6
Age	under 21	43	11.1
	21-40	170	43.8
	41-60	134	34.5
	over 60	41	10.5
Marital status	single	101	26
	married	287	74
Education	primary school	33	8.5
	middle school	220	56.7
	college	119	30.7
Profession	master or above	16	4.1
	services	30	7.7
	government	36	9.3
	farming	17	4.4
	business	65	16.8
	unemployed	39	10.1
	students	99	25.6
	freelance	102	26.3
Information source	advertisement	46	11.9
	agency	68	17.5
	friends	267	68.8
	other	7	1.8
Re-patronage	1 time	119	30.7
	2 times	46	11.9
	3 times	37	9.5
	4 times-	186	47.9
Origin place	Local	151	38.9
	Guangdong	132	34
	mainland	85	21.8
	foreign	20	5.1
Total		388	

IV. DATA ANALYSIS

A. Reliability Analysis

As part of this study, 400 questionnaires were administered randomly to visitors to Chaoshan. A total of 388 valid copies were obtained. Reliability analysis showed that the Cronbach's alpha value of tourist motives is 0.858, the Cronbach's Alpha value of tourist satisfaction is 0.926, and the Cronbach's Alpha value of tourist behavioral intention is 0.788. The value is above 0.70, and therefore the reliability is confirmed.

B. Factor Analysis of Religious Tourism Motivation

The Bartlett ball value of chi-square is 2585.044, which has a significant level. The KMO index is 0.844, which is bigger than 0.80. This means there is are common factors between those variable items. This means the questionnaire is suitable for factor analysis. The principal component extraction method was used and three factors were extracted. The authors identified these three factors as "enriching interpersonal relationship", "having a rest" and "experiencing religious atmosphere". These three factors mean that religious tourists not only enjoy religious culture, but also regard their trip as an opportunity to communicate each other.

C. Factor Analysis of Religious Tourist Satisfaction

After factor analysis of religious tourism motivation, we analyzed religious tourist satisfaction using the factor analysis method. The Bartlett ball value of chi-square is 5135.574, which reached the significant level. The KMO indexes is 0.881, the values are greater than judgment value 0.80. This means there is a common factor between those variable items. Therefore, it is suitable for factor analysis. Those variable items were extracted four factors by using principal component analysis method. Therefore, we identified four factors, which were "temple experience", "management style", "related service" and "transportation".

D. Factor Analysis of Religious Tourist Behavioral Intention

After factor analysis of religious tourist satisfaction, we analyzed religious tourist behavioral intention using the factor analysis method. The Bartlett ball value of chi-square is 971.072, which reached the significant level. The KMO index is 0.711, which is greater than judgement value 0.70. This means there is a common factor between those variable items, and therefore it is suitable for factor analysis. It extracted principal component extraction of two factors. The author identified two factors, which were "revisit intention" and "recommendation intention".

E. Regression Analysis

Regression analysis showed that the motivation of religious tourists could be used to predict the variables for tourists' satisfaction. Satisfaction is the intermediary variable. Behavioral intention is the criterion variable. The Pearson's correlation coefficients of satisfaction and behavior intention were 0.512 and 0.473, respectively. The value of VIF (Variance Inflation Factor) is 1.239, which is less than 10, so the variable relationship has no a total of linear phenomenon, and therefore

there is correlation relationship between tourism motivation, tourist satisfaction and tourist behavior intention. The multiple correlation coefficient is 0.582. The square of the multiple correlation coefficient is 0.339. Regression analysis showed that the motivation and satisfaction variables can explain 33.9% variances of the behavioral intention. Accordingly, tourist motivation has linear positive correlation relationship with religious tourist satisfaction and tourist satisfaction has linear positive correlation relationship with behavior intention. If the tourist's motivation is stronger, the satisfaction will be higher, and tourist behavioral intention is also stronger.

TABLE II
 TOURISM MOTIVATIONS

construct	items	variance
interpersonal relationship	pray to god	.842
	make a wish	.837
	enrich beliefs	.830
leisure	communicate	.823
	enjoy and resting	.803
	meet the mood	.801
	escape daily job	.682
	to be with family	.591
	go hiking	.568
religious atmosphere	enjoy history	.522
	folk customs	.862
	historic culture	.846
	chant sutras	.766
	festival atmosphere	.582

TABLE III
 TOURIST SATISFACTION

construct	items	variance
experience in temple	temple design	.858
	clean environment	.813
	culture authenticity	.803
	landscape	.783
	enjoyment	.727
destination management	management	.847
	professional	.830
	temple introduction	.826
	monk lecture	.699
related service	free books	.554
	talking with staff	.843
transportation	shopping	.818
	hotel	.785
	parking	.736
	bus station	.715
	transportation sign	.660

TABLE IV
 TOURIST BEHAVIORAL INTENTION

construct	items	variance
revisit intention	continue attending	.819
	spend more money	.736
	recommendation	.640
	attend again	.635
recommendation	share tourism feeling	.821
	was up to expectation	.668
	Would recommend to others	.645

V. CONCLUSION

A. Discussion

Based on face-to-face interviews and demographic data analysis, the authors found that most married women in Chaoshan like to participate in religious tourism. The author speculates that this may be because for many married women aged 30-40 years that this is a difficult period in their lives due to pressures from family and career. The Chaoshan religion is may be seen as spiritual ballast which can help them to relieve stress and make friends easily. Partly because of the Cultural Revolution in mainland China, most middle-aged visitors began to work after graduating from high school. And because of many indeterminate factors, they also feel the need for religion to become their spiritual ballast. A feature of the Chaoshan religion is that it is a combination of Buddhism, Taoism and folk beliefs. Local visitors have a profound emotional attachment to temple culture and often attend more than four times a year. They choose to travel by road, and visit for more than one hour at a time. They are more willing to share their beliefs with family and friends. Foreign tourists generally participate in religious tourism as part of a tour group, and most are taking part in religious tourism for the first time. Visitors from other places often have no particular religious belief; however, for geographical reasons, they know more about Chaoshan culture, and as such, choose a religious tour to the region as a way of experiencing it.

The motives of religious tourists are experiencing religious atmosphere, experiencing local culture and taking a rest. Tourists like to share their religious belief and feelings with their friends and relatives, appreciate the temple architecture, pray for their family's well-being, and feel the solemn atmosphere. Motivated by their religious beliefs, visitors go to temples, share their belief with friends, talk with monks and get some religion implications. Most tourists engage in religious tourism for prayer, blessing and worship, experiencing the religious culture in Chaoshan.

The results show that visitor satisfaction of the temple environment is high, while the level of satisfaction related to professional management, service and transportation is low. Those temples perceived to have a sacred, clean environment and the solemn atmosphere will improve religious tourists' satisfaction level. Professional temple management is the measure of whether the temple is effective or not. A professional temple can provide more religion's activities and build a relationship of trust between temples and tourists. Positive and clear expression and explanations in tourist guides can allow visitors to better understand the local culture. At the same time, good accommodation will give visitors a better impression of the temple and convenient transportation will attract more people to visit.

Data analysis showed tourists' behavioral intention correlates with tourist satisfaction. This means high satisfaction level may lead to higher recommendation from tourists; therefore, improving relevant facilities of these temples could attract more visitors and more recommendations. Whether the motivation of tourism is strong or not and the satisfaction is

high or not that will determine whether the visitors are willing to spend more money and time, offer improvement advice and return again or not. After a visit, if the tourists' satisfaction is higher they may think positively about their religious holiday experience. Moreover, they will share the travel experience with others and recommend Chaoshan religious culture to others.

B. Recommendation

Designing an effective marketing plan is necessary to develop the market for religious tourism [6]. Through research and analysis, it can be seen that most tourists' motivation tends to be "religious atmosphere", rather than "have a rest", and "interpersonal relationship". In order to sustain and improve the tourism's satisfaction level, the authors suggest tourist attractions of religion should be paid more attention to, such as religious atmosphere, environment and relevant service level. Moreover, temples should focus on the protection of cultural treasures, invite more monks to visit, increase the storage of religion's resources, and organize believers to join some religion celebration can improve the richness of religion tourism. If the temple improves the "interpersonal relationship" motivation of tourists, then the "related services" satisfaction of tourist can be indirectly improved. At the same time, it will attract more tourists to have "revisit intention".

This study showed that most visitors have lower satisfaction of "related services" and "transportation", which means that the relevant tourism administrative department needs improve transportation facilities to religious tourism attractions, as well as the available accommodation in the surrounding areas. The study also showed that increasing overall visitor satisfaction would not only result in higher tourist numbers, but would also encourage them to be more willing to share their experiences and recommend Chaoshan religious culture to others.

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